

IN VITRO ANTI-DANDRUFF STUDY AND PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF *ALLAMANDA CATHARTICA* L. LEAVES

¹Safeera Mayyeri, ^{2*}Ummu Habeeba, ³Muhsina P.V, ⁴Shahana T, ⁵Ulfath Swaliha K, ⁶Dr. S.V. Rekha, ⁷Dr. S.D. Shanmugakumar

¹Professor in Charge, ^{2,3,4,5}8th Semester Students, ⁶Principal, ⁷Vice Principal, Department of Pharmacognosy, Karuna College of Pharmacy, Thirumittacode, Palakkad, Kerala. Kerala University of Health Sciences, Thrissur, Kerala, India.

Article Received on 28 Feb. 2026,
Article Revised on 18 March 2026,
Article Published on 01 April 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19328909>

*Corresponding Author

Ummu Habeeba

8th Semester Students, Department of Pharmacognosy, Karuna College of Pharmacy, Thirumittacode, Palakkad, Kerala. Kerala University of Health Sciences, Thrissur, Kerala, India.

How to cite this Article: 1Safeera Mayyeri, 2*Ummu Habeeba, 3Muhsina P.V, 4Shahana T, 5Ulfath Swaliha K, 6Dr. S.V. Rekha, 7Dr. S.D. Shanmugakumar (2026). In Vitro Anti-Dandruff Study And Phytochemical Screening Of Aqueous Extract Of Allamanda Cathartica L. Leaves. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(7), 762-770.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The study focuses on the Invitro anti-dandruff study and phytochemical screening of aqueous extract of *Allamanda cathartica* L. leaves dandruff is a common scalp disorder primarily caused by the lipophilic yeast *Malassezia furfur*. Although several synthetic antifungal agents are available for its treatment, prolonged use may lead to adverse effects and the development of resistance. This has increased interest in herbal remedies as safer alternatives. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the antidandruff potential of *Allamanda cathartica* L. leaf extract and to investigate its phytochemical constituents. The study includes leaves collection, authentication, shade dry, powdering and extraction using distilled water by the Maceration method. Preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of carbohydrates, alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, tannins and lipids. The anti-dandruff activity of the aqueous extract

assessed against *Malassezia furfur* using the agar well diffusion method, with Ketoconazole as the standard drug. The extract exhibits a measurable zone of inhibition at higher concentrations, indicating significant anti-dandruff activity. The study confirms that *Allamanda cathartica* L. possesses promising anti-dandruff potential may serve as natural, effective alternative for the management of dandruff, subject to further formulation

development and clinical evaluation.

KEYWORDS: *Allamanda cathartica*, Anti-dandruff, *Malassezia furfur*, Phytochemical screening, Agar well diffusion, Ketoconazole.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants serve as valuable sources of therapeutic agents and bioactive compounds. Each plant consists of several important ingredients that can be used in medical field, and being involved in the development of different kind of drugs.^[1] The World Health Organization estimates that a large percentage of the global population relies on herbal medicine for primary healthcare. Dandruff is a chronic scalp condition characterized by flaking and itching. It is mainly associated with the overgrowth of *Malassezia furfur*, a lipophilic yeast that metabolizes scalp sebum and produces inflammatory by-products. Conventional treatments include antifungal agents such as ketoconazole, zinc pyrithione, selenium sulfide, and salicylic acid.^[2] However, long-term use may cause irritation and resistance. *Allamanda cathartica*, commonly known as Golden Trumpet, belongs to the family Apocynaceae.^[3] The plant contains iridoids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and phenolic compounds, which are known for antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties.

This study investigates in vitro anti-dandruff activity of its aqueous leaf extract against *Malassezia furfur* and also focuses on the phytochemical screening of its aqueous leaf extract to identify bioactive constituents responsible for anti-dandruff activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Plant material: Dried leaves of *Allamanda cathartica* L. Chemicals: Sabouraud Dextrose Agar
Olive oil Ketoconazole Distilled water.

Microorganism: *Malassezia furfur* (MTCC 1374)

METHODS

1. PLANT MATERIAL COLLECTION AND AUTHENTICATION

Fresh leaves of *Allamanda cathartica* were collected from Malappuram district, Kerala, and authenticated by the Department of Botany, NSS Arts and Science College, Palakkad.

2. PHARMACOGNOSTIC STUDY

Macroscopic study: An organoleptic and external morphological character of freshly collected

leaves was observed under magnifying lens.

Microscopic Study: Thin transverse sections of leaves were prepared by free-hand sectioning and stained with safranin to detect lignified tissues. Microscopic evaluation included determination of leaf constants.^[4]

- Stomatal Number
- Stomatal Index
- Vein Islet Number
- Vein Termination Number

3. DRYING AND COARSE POWDERING OF PLANT MATERIAL

The leaves of *Allamanda cathartica* L. were thoroughly washed in running water and shade dried. It was then ground to coarse powder.

4. PREPARATION OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT

Aqueous extract of *A.cathartica* leaves were prepared by cold maceration method. 5 g of accurately weight powdered air-dried drug was macerated with 100 ml of chloroform water in a closed flask for twenty-four hours, shaking frequently during six hours and allow standing for eighteen hours. It was then filtered rapidly, taking precautions against loss of solvent. After maceration, filter the mixture using muslin cloth into a clean beaker. Squeeze the residue gently to recover as much extract as possible. 25 ml of the filtrate was evaporated to dryness and dried to a constant weight and weighed Store the extract in a refrigerator at 4⁰C. For longer storage, consider concentrating or drying the extract.^[5]

Extractive value (%) = (Weight of extract(g) / Weight of herb(g)) × 100

5. PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING

Qualitative Analysis Standard tests were performed to detect:^[6]

- Carbohydrates (Molisch's test)
- Alkaloids (Mayer's, Dragendorff's tests)
- Glycosides (Trim-Hill test)
- Flavonoids (Alkaline reagent test)
- Tannins (Ferric chloride test)
- Lipids (Salkowski test)
- Proteins (Biuret test)

6. INVITRO ANTI-DANDRUFF ACTIVITY

The antidandruff activity of the test samples was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method. *Malassezia furfur* was cultured in Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA or Sab Dex) which is specifically supplemented with Olive oil (1% or 2%). The cultures are incubated at 30°C–37°C for 48-72 hrs and adjusted to a standardized inoculum, then uniformly swabbed onto sterile agar plates. Wells of 6 mm diameter were aseptically punched and filled with 50 and 100 µL of Aqueous extract and Ketoconazole (100 µg/10 µg) as the positive control. Plates are allowed to diffuse for 30 minutes and incubated at 30°C – 37°C for 48 hrs to 7 days and the diameter of zones of inhibition were measured in millimetres after incubation to assess antifungal efficacy.^[7]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

The study involved pharmacognostic study, phytochemical screening and invitro anti-dandruff study of *Allamanda cathartica* L.

1. PHARMACOGNOSTIC STUDY

Macroscopic study

Table 1: macroscopic study of *A.cathartica*.

Characteristics	Description
Family	Apocynaceae
Leaf type	Simple
Leaf arrangement	Whorled (usually 3-4 leaves at a node), sometimes opposite.
Leaf shape	Elliptic to oblong - lanceolate
Leaf size	8-15cm long and 3-5cm wide
Apex	Acute to acuminate
Base	Cuneate to attenuate
Margin	Entire
Upper surface	Smooth, glossy, dark green
Lower surface	Slightly paler green, smooth
Venation	Pinnate, reticulate
Texture	Leathery (coriaceous)
Petiole	Short or nearly sessile
Odour	Characteristics, faint
Special features	Prominent midrib on lower surface; milky latex exudes when fresh leaf is broken

Microscopic study

1. Transverse section of *A.cathartica* was observed under microscope:

Fig.1: T.S. of *A.cathartica*.

2. Stomatal number and Stomatal index of *A.cathartica* were determined: Stomatal number was found to be 160.

Stomatal index was found to be 22.2%

Fig.2: Determination of stomatal number and Stomatal index.

3. Vein islet and Vein termination number of *A.cathartica* were determined: Vein islet number was found to be 12.

Vein termination number was found to be 11.

Fig.3: Determination of Vein islet and Vein termination number.

2. EXTRACTION

Extractive value was determined and was found to be 20.49%

3. PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING

Table 2: Phytochemical constituents of *A.cathartica* aqueous extract.

SL.NO	Phytochemical constituents	Result Obtained
1	Carbohydrate	+
2	Reducing sugar	+
3	Alkaloids	+
4	Glycosides	+
5	Flavonoids	+
6	Tannins	+
7	Lipids	+
8	Proteins	-

4. IN VITRO ANTI DANDRUFF ACTIVITY

The aqueous extract demonstrated concentration-dependent anti-dandruff activity against *Malassezia furfur*. The 100 μ L concentration showed a significant zone of inhibition compared to 50 μ L. Ketoconazole exhibited a larger zone of inhibition, serving as a positive control.

Table 3: The Anti-dandruff activity of the Aqueous extract and Ketoconazole.

Microorganism	Aq-50 μ l	Aq -100 μ l	Ketoconazole(mm) 100 μ l/10-100 μ g
<i>Malassezia furfur</i>	0	14	18

Graph 1: The Anti-dandruff activity of the Aqueous and Ketoconazole.

Fig 4: The Anti-dandruff activity of the Aqueous and Ketoconazole.

DISCUSSION

The washed, shade-dried leaves were powdered and evaluated for anti-dandruff activity against *Malassezia furfur*. Pharmacognostic analysis (macro and microscopic) confirmed plant authenticity, with leaf constants within acceptable limits. Phytochemical screening revealed alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, and lipids, compounds known for anti-dandruff and antioxidant effects. Using the agar well diffusion method, the aqueous extract showed no inhibition at 50 μ L but produced a 14 mm inhibition zone at 100 μ L, indicating moderate activity compared with ketoconazole. These findings support its traditional use for scalp disorders and suggest potential for further study using advanced extraction and formulation methods.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that *Allamanda cathartica* leaf extract has noticeable anti-dandruff activity against *Malassezia furfur*, likely due to natural compounds such as flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and glycosides. Although its effect was weaker than ketoconazole, the extract demonstrated moderate anti-dandruff action at higher concentrations. These findings support the plant's traditional use for scalp and skin problems and suggest it could be a safer, plant-based alternative for dandruff control. Further research is needed to isolate active compounds, improve extraction methods, and confirm safety and effectiveness through animal and clinical studies.

This study highlights *Allamanda cathartica* as a promising natural anti-dandruff agent. Future work should focus on isolating active anti-dandruff compounds, optimizing extraction methods, and developing herbal formulations such as shampoos or creams. Clinical and in-vivo studies are needed to confirm safety and efficacy, while advanced delivery systems and patent opportunities may support improved effectiveness and commercialization.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Many thanks to **ALMIGHTY GOD**, for it he who began this work in us and carried it to completion. It is he who has blessed us with the people whose names we feel privileged to mention here.

We extend my heartfelt gratitude to my Guide, **Ms. SAFEERA MAYYERI**, for their invaluable guidance, encouragement, and expertise throughout the course of this study on the **INVITRO ANTI-DANDRUFF STUDY AND PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF *Allamanda cathartica* L. LEAVES** Their mentorship has been a cornerstone of this research.

We are deeply thankful to our Principal, **Dr: S V REKHA**, for their constant support and for providing the necessary facilities to carry out this research. Our sincere thanks to our Vice Principle, **Dr. S D SHANMUGAKUMAR**, for their encouragement and for fostering an environment conducive to research and learning.

We are also grateful to all the **TEACHERS** and **NON-TEACHING STAFF** members of the department for their assistance and cooperation during various stages of this work. Their dedication and efforts ensured a smooth and productive research experience.

A special word of gratitude goes to our **PARENTS**, whose unwavering support, encouragement, and sacrifices have been our greatest source of strength. Their belief in us has always motivated us to strive for excellence.

We would like to express my sincere gratitude to our **FRIENDS** who have supported us throughout this project. Your encouragement, advice, and camaraderie have been instrumental in helping us complete this work.

Finally, we express our sincere appreciation to the **MANAGEMENT** for providing the resources and infrastructure necessary for this study. Their commitment to academic and research excellence has been instrumental in the successful completion of this project.

Thank you all for your invaluable contributions to this endeavour.

REFERENCES

1. Yuan H, Ma Q, Ye L, Piao G. The traditional medicine and modern medicine from natural products. *Molecules*, 2016; 21(5): 559.
2. Lee JH, Lee JS. Chemical composition and antifungal activity of plant essential oils against *Malassezia furfur*. *Korean J Microbiol Biotechnol*, 2010; 38(3): 315–321.
3. United States Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service. *Allamanda cathartica* L. Plant profile. Washington (DC): USDA, 2021; 1–2.
4. Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission. *Indian pharmacopoeia*. Vol I. Ghaziabad: Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, 2018; 232–234.
5. Kokate CK, Purohit AP, Gokhale SB. *Pharmacognosy*. 50th ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan, 2014.
6. Rageeb MMU, Baviskar KD, Patil NG. *Practical pharmaceutical microbiology*. Pune: Pee Vee (Regd.), 2019.
7. Ashbee HR, Scheynius A. *Malassezia*. In: Ashbee HR, Bignell EM, editors. *Pathogenic yeasts*. The yeast handbook. Berlin Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 2010; 209–230.